

Dynamic response enhancement of BDFIG using vector control scheme based internal model control

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ABSTRACT

Double fed induction generator (DFIG) has shown tremendous success in wind turbines due to its flexibility and ability to regulate the active and reactive power. However, the presence of brushes and slip rings affects its reliability, stability, and power quality. Furthermore, it does not provide promising outcomes in case of faults even in presence of the crowbar circuit. In contrast, the brushless doubly fed induction generator (BDFIG) is a more reliable option for wind turbines than its mentioned counterpart due to the absence of the brushes and slip rings. This research work as such attempts to improve the dynamic performance of the vector control (VC) oriented power winding (PW) stator flux-based BDFIG by optimally selecting the proportional-integral (PI) gains through internal model control (IMC) approach. The proposed control scheme is utilized to regulate the speed, torque, and reactive power of the considered BDFIG independently. Contrary to the previous literature where the “trial and error method” is generally utilized, the current research work uses the IMC for selecting the most suitable PI parameters, thus reduces the complexity, time consumption, and uncertainty in optimal selection. The considered BDFIG based wind turbine with the proposed control scheme provides a better BDFIG control design with an enhanced dynamic response as compared to that of the same with DFIG under identical operating conditions and system configurations.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The need for electrical energy is increasing due to the rapidly increasing population and users' power demand for a good quality of life [1]. This continuous increase in power demand creates several challenges for the electric power companies such as overloading of the existing generating units, transmission lines, transformers, and feeders [2]. Furthermore, the environmental and economic impact of such power systems made them outdated for electricity generation [3]. It is for the mentioned reasons that the trend of relying on fossil fuel-based centralized power systems is declining worldwide and decentralized green energy sources such as wind, solar and sea tides are considered as potential candidates for power generation [4], [5]. Among the stated green energy options, wind energy has shown quite promising results in

terms of reliability and efficiency [6]. However, it has been observed that the increasing power in the field of wind energy within the existing power system has introduced few new tasks in terms of grid codes for the advanced generating units, power electronic interfacing devices, and control strategies [7]. The BDFIG has excellent low voltage ride through (LVRT) handling characteristics, improved dynamic response, and most importantly, it does not contain any carbon brushes and slip rings [8]. It is worthwhile to mention here that, similar to the other wind farm machines, the speed and torque of the BDFIG needs to be regulated according to the desired operating condition through a controller with a particular control scheme.

Several control strategies have been developed for controlling BDFIG behavior. The researchers have attempted to control the BDFIG through model predictive virtual power control in [9], direct power controller (DPC) in [10], predictive torque controller by matrix converter in [11], and indirect stator quantities control in [12], however, the mentioned control schemes lags the optimal regulation of speed and reactive power with suitable dynamic response. To overcome the stated issue, the authors have utilized one of the most prominent control schemes called vector control (VC) [13], [14]. It is important to mention that the VC is generally utilized to control the machine side converter (MSC) and grid side converter (GSC) through fuzzy logic (FL) controller [15], controlled hamiltonian system [16], neural wavelet network [17], and Feedback linearization [18]. However, the difficult computations restrict the usage of these controllers into industry. One of the effective solutions of the mention problem is to use conventional PI regulator in VC as done in references [19], [20].

Owing to time constraints and complexity in conventional PI tuning approaches such as “trial and error” and Ziegler-Nichols, this research utilizes the internal model control approach to optimally tune the PI regulators; thus achieves the optimal dynamic response of the proposed BDFIG. The IMC is an analytical PI parameter selection method that considers the system parameters for compensating its open loop poles with the zeros of the PI controller, thus delivers the desired closed-loop bandwidth and time constant. Most importantly, it simplifies the control design procedure and eliminates the need for time-consuming trial-and-error step. To prove the effectiveness of the proposed method, its dynamic response is examined under different operating mechanism as such variable wind speed and reactive power change. The major contributions of this study are highlighted is being as:

- a) IMC approach for obtaining optimal PI gains in VC scheme based BDFIG is comprehensively modeled and explored in order to obtain the optimal dynamic response of the machine.
- b) A detailed version of the designed control scheme is made depends on several performance indicators such as speed regulation and reactive power control under different conditions.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows; Section 2 describes the operation and modeling of the machine. The converter along with the proposed IMC PI gain selection approach is discussed in Section 3. Section 4 describes the proposed VC scheme. The results are presented in Section 5. Finally, Section 6 presents the conclusion of the paper.

2. BDFIG OPERATION AND MODELLING

There are three modes of operation for the BDFIM machine i.e., cascaded Mode, induction Mode, and synchronous mode. Mostly, the synchronous operation of BDFIM is considered for the wind turbine which is obtained by coupling the stator windings while PW is connected with the grid, and CW is linked to the machine with the help of a power electronic converter. The active and reactive power of the machine is controlled by regulating CW voltage and frequency. Since the machine has two stator windings namely power winding and control winding, the number of poles for both windings must be different to avoid direct magnetic coupling [21]. The cross-coupling for PW and CW allows the control of PW current with CW supply. The relation between the number of rotors turns (N_r), the number of poles for power winding (P_p) and control winding (P_c) is given in (1) and induced rotor frequencies is given in (2):

$$N_r = P_p + P_c; \quad P_p \neq P_c \tag{1}$$

$$\omega_r = \frac{\omega_1 + \omega_2}{P_p + P_c} \tag{2}$$

Where ω_r represents the rotor natural frequency, ω_1 and ω_2 are the natural powe winding frequencies and control winding, respectively. To design an appropriate controller for the considered grid-tied BDFIG and to evaluate and enhance the machine’s dynamic performance, its mathematical model is essentially required. Since the proposed controller is aligned to the PW flux frame [22], hence; in (3) can be written as:

$$\lambda_{pd} = |\lambda_p| \text{ and } \lambda_{pq} = 0 \tag{3}$$

where λ_{pd} and λ_{pq} denote the d and q components of power winding flux respectively. The voltage and flux equations for the power winding are represented as [23].

$$V_{pdq} = I_{pdq}R_p - j\omega_1\lambda_{pdq} + \frac{d\lambda_{pdq}}{dt} \quad (4)$$

$$\lambda_{pdq} = L_p I_{pdq} + M_{pr} I_{rdq} \quad (5)$$

Where V_{pdq} represents the d and q component of power winding voltage and I_{pdq} denote the d and q component of power winding currents. R_p , L_p , M_{pr} , I_{rdq} represents the is power winding resistance, power winding inductance, mutual inductance between the rotor and power winding, d component of rotor current, and d component of rotor current respectively. Similarly, the mathematical representation for the CW voltage and flux can be represented as;

$$V_{cdq} = I_c R_c - j(\omega_1 - N_r \omega_r) \lambda_{cdq} + \frac{d\lambda_{cdq}}{dt} \quad (6)$$

$$\lambda_{cdq} = L_c I_{cdq} + M_{cr} I_{rdq} \quad (7)$$

where V_{cdq} represents the d and q component of control winding voltage, I_{cdq} symbolize the d and q component of control winding currents, R_c is control winding resistance, λ_{cdq} shows d and q component of control winding flux respectively, L_c is the control winding inductance, M_{cr} is the mutual inductance between rotor and control winding. Finally, the RW voltage and flux can be presented mathematically as provided in (10)-(13)

$$V_{rdq} = I_{rdq}R_r - j(\omega_1 - P_p \omega_r)\lambda_{rdq} + \frac{d\lambda_{rdq}}{dt} \quad (8)$$

$$\lambda_{rdq} = M_{pr} I_{pdq} + M_{cr} I_{cdq} + L_r I_{rdq} \quad (9)$$

$$\lambda_{rq} = M_{pr} I_{pq} + M_{cr} I_{cq} + L_r I_{rq} \quad (10)$$

where V_{rdq} represents the d and q component of rotor winding voltage, R_r is rotor winding resistance, λ_{rdq} represents the d and q component of rotor winding flux respectively while L_r denotes the rotor winding inductance. Similarly, the generated machine torque T_e is given as following I_m represents the magnetizing inductance:

$$T_e = -\frac{3}{2}P_p I_m [\lambda_p^* I_p] - \frac{3}{2}P_c I_m [\lambda_c^* I_c] \quad (11)$$

3. PROPOSED IMC BASED VC SCHEME

A vector controller aligned on the PW reference frame is proposed to change the speed and reactive power independently [24]. The reactive power and speed are calculated analytically using the mathematical model of BDFIM while the PI controller gains are derived through the IMC method. In the vector control scheme, the dq components of PW and CW currents are regulated to obtain the desired reactive power and speed of the machine. The controlled signal obtained after conversion from DQ to ABC is fed to the PWM block which accordingly switches the inverter to inject the controlled amount of power into the grid. It is important to note that the current study utilizes only MSC to change the speed and reactive power of the machine.

3.1. Analytical IMC model for MSI

In this subsection, IMC method for selecting the PI regulator gains in the proposed vector control scheme is discussed in detail. The block diagram of proposed IMC based BDFIG control scheme is depicted in Figure 1. As from Figure 1 that the MSI is directly connected to the CW and is used to regulate the reactive power using d component while active power/speed with q component of the current [25]. The frequency of the PW supply is set as 50 Hz throughout the simulation time. The major components of the proposed control scheme are described is being as.

Figure 1. MSI with IMC method

3.1.1. PW current controllers

The PW current is regulated with the help of CW current by providing cross-coupling between two windings. The nonlinear dynamic model of the proposed grid-tied BDFIG system is represented by (12).

$$I_{cdq} = y_1 I_{pdq} + y_2 \frac{dI_{pdq}}{dt} - y_3 \lambda_p - y_4 \frac{d\lambda_{pdq}}{dx} - j\omega_1 y_4 \lambda_{pdq} + j\omega_1 y_2 I_{pdq} - j\omega_1 I_{cdq} \quad (12)$$

From the above equations the direct relation between PW and CW is extracted as follows;

$$I_c = y_1 I_p + y_2 \frac{dI_p}{dt} \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{I_p}{I_c} = \frac{1}{y_2 s + y_1}, \quad \frac{I_p}{I_c} = \frac{1}{y_2 s + y_1} \quad (14)$$

To initiate the IMC based parameter extraction process, the rise time tr_p and bandwidth BW of the system is calculated as $95e^{-3}$ and 0.1841. A vector control scheme is used to obtain high control performance of MSI whose PI regulators are tuned with the IMC method. Furthermore, the external disturbance is avoided by using feed-forward compensation. The proportional and integral gains (Kp_p and Ki_p) for outer loop PI regulator can be calculated by using (15).

$$Kp_p = 2 * pi * BW_p * y_2, \quad Ki_p = 2 * pi * BW_p * y_1 \quad (15)$$

3.1.2. CW current controller

CW voltage is regulated with the help of CW current as expressed in (16). The mentioned equations show the direct relationship between CW current and voltage in the proposed vector control scheme.

$$v_{cdq} = d_1 I_{cdq} + d_2 \frac{dI_{cdq}}{dt} + (-d_3 + jd_4)\lambda_{pdq} + d_5 \frac{d\lambda_{pdq}}{dx} + (d_6 + jd_7)I_{pdq} - jd_8 I_{cdq} \quad (16)$$

Similarly using the relationship between CW voltage and CW current is expressed as:

$$v_c = d_1 I_c + d_2 \frac{dI_c}{dt}, \quad \frac{I_c}{v_c} = \frac{1}{d_2 s + d_1} \quad (17)$$

The expressions for calculating Kp_c and Ki_c values for the CW current control through the IMC method are provided in (18):

$$Kp_c = 2 * pi * BW_c * d_2, \quad Ki_c = 2 * pi * BW_c * d_1 \quad (18)$$

3.1.3. Speed control design

Since the PW voltage is taken as reference, therefore the d component of PW flux remains constant. The generated torque for the machine can be calculated as:

$$T_e = -\frac{3}{2} (P_p + P_c) |\lambda_p| I_{pq} \quad (19)$$

4.1. Case 1: speed regulation

Control of the rotor speed is very crucial in the application of wind turbines where the wind speed is unpredictable. Therefore, in this case, the speed of the machine is regulated between 0 to 70 rad/s at the constant torque of 0 N.m and the reactive power of 500 VAR. The simulation is performed to see the impact of changing speed on PW, CW, and reactive power. The corresponding response of the system is depicted in Figure 3(a) while its impact on the CW current, PW current, and reactive power is shown in Figures 3(b)-(d) respectively.

As can be seen from the mentioned figures that the machine shows good dynamic response and tracks the speed changes effectively. The controller is able to regulate the speed in a wide range of $\pm 30\%$ of 52 radians/sec; thus, maintains the stable operation of the system. The PW, CW currents and reactive power follows the changes effectively without any noticeable overshoots. It is important to note that, when the speed of the BDFIM is changed from sub-natural to super-natural speed, the CW currents vary their sequence to uphold synchronous operation as evident from Figure 3(b). The synchronous speed of the machine is 52 rad/sec in this paper.

Figure 3. These figures are; (a) speed regulation, (b) control winding current, (c) power winding current, (d) reactive power

4.2. Case 2: reactive power control

In this case, the effect of changes in reactive power on system stability is examined. Step changes in the reactive power of the machine are made at 0, 2, 4, 6, and 8 seconds of the simulation run as depicted in Figure 4(a). The corresponding impact of such sharp changes in reactive power, speed, PW current, and CW current is depicted in Figures 4(b)-(d) respectively.

It can be observed from Figure 4 that the changes in reactive power affect the speed, PW current, and CW current, however, the proposed control scheme effectively manages to maintain the stable operation of the machine with a suitable dynamic response. The Figure 4 show that the proposed IMC based vector control scheme is able to track the changes in the reactive power, thus making the BDFIG supply the required reactive power to the grid during the normal and fault conditions.

Figure 4. These figures are; (a) reactive power, (b) speed regulator, (c) power winding current, (d) control winding current

5. CONCLUSION

This paper presented an IMC based vector control scheme for BDFIM. The proposed control scheme can regulate the speed and reactive power of the BDFIG effectively with a suitable dynamic response. To enhance the transient response of the system during normal operating conditions, the gains of the PI regulators are selected using the IMC method. To validate the effectiveness of the proposed control scheme, its performance is evaluated under sharp variations in different system control parameters such as speed, torque, and reactive power. The proposed control scheme tracks the changes in the mentioned variables accurately with excellent dynamic response and maintains the stable operation of the system; thus, proves the effectiveness of the proposed control scheme.

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